

00. Panel/Round table

Kierkegaard and Aquinas: On Epistemological Boundaries towards to become Virtuous.

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Kierkegaard and Aquinas on Epistemological Boundaries towards becoming Virtuous.

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This presentation correlates Kierkegaard and Aquinas on becoming a virtuous self. Doing so, it identifies the epistemological boundaries to be traversed. Each author shares the same starting point of having to build-up the self, in Kierkegaardian discourse, to overcome an ontological fracture that defines their theological anthropology. For Aquinas that starting point implies becoming virtuous through educating the self. Each author has his own configuration of concepts. The relevant ones for our purpose will be correlated by going beyond semantics, to enhance understanding the epistemological aspect of boundaries to be crossed in becoming genuinely a person.

The human self for Aquinas and Kierkegaard, is a composite reality, having spirit infused in the body at the time of creation. Thereby it has both simultaneously a finite and infinite reality through which it stands in relation to the Eternal. An ontological rupture, becoming separated from the Eternal through sin, occasioned a predicament for the self. Spirit is longing to become related absolutely to the Eternal. Aquinas holds that educating the self to become virtuous in attaining the highest good is to overcome the rupture. Kierkegaard proposes that self is relational, is to relate finitely to finitude and simultaneously infinitely and absolutely to the eternal happiness Christianity promises. Overcoming the ontological rupture implicates, building up the self. For Aquinas, it is traversing three levels -sensible, rational, and virtuous- in his theory of knowledge to attain the highest good. Those three levels are correlated here with Kierkegaard's three existential spheres: aesthetic, ethical and the religious in overcoming the rupture.

To describe briefly, the Kierkegaardian spheres, the **Aesthetic** is indicative of a life whose reliance is solely on the senses, thus subject to ever-changing desires and contingencies of existence that may lead to despair until the infused spirit is slowly awakened and seeking to become related to the eternal. Choosing or committing oneself to a good such as expressing the cardinal virtues, is a step to relating the spirit to the eternal, and thereby, crossing the boundary of the aesthetic to the **Ethical**¹. This relation is also associated with despair, namely despair over the good, whether what one has willed truly and sincerely is the good or is remaining loyal to it.

¹ EO2, 255.

Or one may choose to persist earnestly and cross the boundary into the **Religious** by deepening commitment through relating to a *telos* that is an eternal source of comfort – Providence or God. Christianity representing a heightened mode of existence requires taking a leap to acknowledge the self's reliance on Divine assistance and readiness to accept forgiveness of sins. The highest mode of existing religiously is associated with Christian virtues summed up in the Gospel command to love our neighbor. Doing that, is becoming fully an authentic self, standing before God in striving to overcome the ontological rupture.

For Aquinas, education is a means of progression from the sensitive, to the rational and then, to virtue. Sensation is the material from where the intellect abstracts, posing such truths as ends for the Will to attain² *hic et nunc*, to order these ends or loves, is the path to happiness, but is constantly obscured by sin. This fracture between reason and will –sin- is the main obstacle to achieve spiritual completeness. To get from who we are, to whom we could become: From a human nature, which pursues worldly or relative choices to a supranatural, spiritual and free second nature, which pursues the absolute: God as *telos*, or happiness which perfects our ever-craving appetites.

Aquinas' **teleological** starting point is his aim, although unclear at first: -First in intention, last in achievement-. It clarifies by becoming accomplished: The person craves for happiness which is ultimately God: his fulfilment, but the way is paved with partial goods which confuse and deviate the path, he must constantly recalculate and reorder his loves³. To see clearly, -a very personal process that depends on specific epistemological frameworks, and particular situations, to act upon⁴-, repetition is necessary to create a habit, which joins thought and the action-end in one unfractured decision. Thus, correctly aimed, every day, simple deeds take the person towards the good, developing within a second firmer nature, stabilizing passions, and focusing the mind from lesser distractions. So, repetition is the way to travel lighter towards God, discriminating among worldly distractions, redirecting human boundaries to spiritual scopes. Such crossing back and forth between the intellect and the will, builds the bridge to cross the boundaries between the epistemological and practical realms. In Kierkegaard's words: "Learning to relate absolutely to the absolute and relatively to the relative"⁵.

For both authors: repetition ends in reconciliation with God: which means the split in our being is healed, and our sins are purified, consequently derives in a new birth⁶: A redemption from the captivity of sin. The second time is decisive because by redoing we gain consciousness and hence, freedom. Deepening into one's self to bring it forth into the light of God, without losing the -step by step- gained traits, in

² Cfr. Idem 13.6.

³ "*Virtus est ordo amoris*". Augustine de Hippo. De Moribus Ecclesiae. Cap 15.

⁴ "As it is to each one, such an end appears to him". Eth Nic. 3:5.

⁵ CUP. 387-555.

⁶ I-II. q. XIX ad.10.

the self's personality. This is how virtue habitually upbuilds the individual by repetition.

Christian virtues are products of free choice and striving, as character traits, they are God's achievement in us, they are personal modes of appropriation of God's love in us which is highly relevant to our eternal happiness, the infinite comes to exist in us in a habitual everyday manner, leaving by its repetition a dispositional trace in our thinking and doing, which Aquinas defines as virtue.

For Kierkegaard, repetition is a transcendent, it is the religious movement which reduces humanity to the absurd. The dialectic of repetition means newness, but the very fact that this happens makes the repetition something new⁷. It is only God who can take us out of our lack of spirit, who leads us to self-knowledge. The leap into the religious sphere opens a vast space for the relationship with God, but it is necessary to first "unhumanize" or "unworldinize": an attempt to see ourselves through God's perspective.

The religious state corresponds to the eschatological re-creation which brings the "heavenly man"⁸ or second nature out.

Redemption is a transition from not being –in which sin consists- into being, a new man in Christ. Accordingly, the leap can be regarded as a sign of God's intervention in human history. To Kierkegaard's mind, existence is not immanent nor self-referential, it develops constantly and ultimately "before God". In this sense, a distinction between -profane, quantitative time: *χρονος*-, and a deep meaningful present -sacred or qualitative time: *καιρος*–: the crucial instant in which time and eternity touch each other⁹ describe the existential or virtuous choice towards God.

As for Aquinas' being God the *Summum Bonum*, the reason sets it as the *telos*, for the will, to reach¹⁰. This is reconciliation, choosing the optimal consciously and freely: God, who is the paradigm of virtue. Looking forward to and deciding for it, is how Christian virtues are developed¹¹.

Both authors' parallel paths cross epistemic and existential boundaries which upbring the self to the spiritual realm, but, the emphasis is set in the ever-changing relational reality -*inter esse*- the person becomes through his conscious approach to God¹². The true singular person, at the peak of his potential, is *hic et nunc*, his relationship with God.

⁷ R, 149.

⁸ 2 Cor: 5, 17; Rev: 21, 5.

⁹ CA, 87.

¹⁰ I-II, q. XI, ad 4. *Confer ea quæ dicta sunt*: I, q. XIX ad 8; Et q. XXII ad 4.

¹¹ I-II, q. LXI, ad 4.

¹² "To relate to God is to have conscience". WL 143.

In Kierkegaard's words: "True love is a super-human goal, which can be achieved only through a divine upbuilding. The love among the Divine persons and the love from God to human beings is the theological ground for any work of **charity**"¹³.

In Aquinas': "Friendship with God, which is called charity, cannot intercede for anyone, unless he believes that there is a conversation of with God, and hopes that he belongs to this society: it is impossible for charity to exist without **faith** and **hope**"¹⁴. **Prudence** is of course central in this intertwining, as Kierkegaard also calls his readers to careful reflection and deliberation that will lead them a virtuous life: the ability to discern the way to eternal happiness.

The single individual relates himself first to God and then to the community, but this first relation is most important, even though he does not reject the second. The opposition between the human being: "sensate-psychical-person" (*δε φυσικος*) and the "spiritual-person", (*δε πνευματικος*) reflects on Kierkegaard's dichotomic conception of love¹⁵, the strongest of passions, and Aquinas' order of loves.

For Kierkegaard, "Ethical virtue has the passions for its material, reason for its form"¹⁶. For Aquinas, "Moral virtue perfects the appetitive part of the soul [passions] by directing it towards the good as defined by reason"¹⁷. Virtue is not the goal, God is, virtue is only the path that leads the self to his *telos*.

To conclude: Every virtue has a deepening sense into the self, the connection among them implies a self-understanding that is the existential synthesis of the temporal and the eternal, the finite and the infinite. The purpose of virtue ethics is to make human beings wise and complete their spiritual potential. So "the most that a human being can do for another is to help him to become himself, free, independent: his own master"¹⁸.

(1647 words without references)

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¹³ WL, 265-266.

¹⁴ I-II q. LXV. ad 5.

¹⁵ 1 Cor: 2, 14-15.

¹⁶ CUP, quoted in Roberts and Evans, "Ethics", 226.

¹⁷ I-II. 59.4.

¹⁸ WL, 274.

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